

The secret of Abraham's spell is hidden in the Holy Qur'an

Prof. Dr Kazi Abdul Mannan

Chairperson

Center for Academic & Professional Career Development and Research (CAPCDR)

Dhaka, Bangladesh

Email: drkaziabdulmannan@gmail.com

ORCID:0000-0002-7123-132X

Abstract: The Holy Qur'an mentions the name Ibrahim (إبراهيم) in 15 places and Ibrahi-i-m (إبراهيم) in 54 places, a total of 69 times (except the pronoun), which is translated as Abraham in all famous English translations of the world. Two types of spelling of the same person are followed in the Holy Qur'an. Unfortunately, no analysis is found anywhere as to why there is such a discrepancy in the spelling of the name. Therefore, the basic purpose of this study is to find out whether there is an interpretation of the two types of spelling mentioned in the Holy Qur'an. To achieve this objective, the relevant verses of the Holy Qur'an and also other Holy scriptures have been reviewed through content analysis. The results showed that there are no differences between the same individuals. Ibrahim (إبراهيم) mentioned in the Holy Qur'an was given to his family which means the father of a nation. However, Ibrahi-i-m (إبراهيم) was the new name changed by the Lord by defining the term father of nations. Although there are different religious opinions, even today, he is identified as the father of many nations according to the holy scriptures of the three religions. Therefore, this study has concluded that the orthography mentioned in the Holy Qur'an is not a clerical or grammatical error rather it opens up a bridge between the religious original scriptures.

Keywords: Abraham; Christianity; Islam; Judaism; orthography

1. Introduction

Abraham is a great man of the three main religions Christianity, Islam, and Judaism. Although these three religions have historical differences according to their respective scriptures and other studies. This study completely refrains from exploring any such controversial issues. In the Holy Qur'an, the name Abraham is mentioned a total of 69 times (see Annexure-I), in each of which all the famous English translators of the world have translated Abraham and the same practice has been followed by the local translators of different languages. But in the Holy Qur'an, it is seen that only in the second Surah (Al-Baqara) was Ibrahim 15 times, and in the rest of the surahs 54 times Ibrahi-i-m followed. The Holy Qur'an itself refers to it as the scripture of Almighty Allah and there is no conflict in this belief even though other issues are disputed among the more than 180 million Muslims in the world. The Muslim world believes that the Holy Qur'an is completely accurate and the basis of their belief is the Holy Qur'an itself (Q 2:2; 10:37).

There are abundant studies on Abraham around the world. Followers of Judaism based their investigations on their scriptures and religious scriptures (Mojzes 2022; Siker 2009; Gregory 2008), which to be continued. There are many explorations related to Christianity depending on their religious schools (Feldman 2011; Cooper 2000; Hall 1988). Similarly, in Islam, it has done a lot of studies on the Holy Qur'an and their theological analysis relies on their sects (Mirza 2011; Ben-Ari 2007; Goshen-Gottstein 2002). Moreover, it can be seen that numerous studies have done a comparative scholarship with these three religions with various facts and incidents centered on Abraham (Morteza 2023; Bashir et al 2022; Rumaisah 2022). However, in all these studies, Ibrahim has been identified with one name, that is Abraham, where there is no discussion about this two-way spelling of the Holy Qur'an.

The Holy Qur'an has mentioned several times that this scripture is a must-learn for all people (Q 2:21; Q 2:161; Q 4:1; Q 4:170) (not only for Muslims), which comes from the only creator of the universe (Q 2:174; Q 4:174; Q 6:92; Q 7:196; Q 6:92; Q 7:196; Q 14:1, Q 16:64; Q18:82; Q17:106; Q 21:10; Q 26:192; Q 29:47; Q 39:1; Q 40:2; Q 41:2; Q 45:2; Q 56:80; Q 69:43), in which there is no mistake or even any kind of doubt (Q 2:2; Q:10:37; Q 32:2). At various verses in the Holy Qur'an, a challenge has been thrown that even if all the creations try together, it is not possible to write a similar book (Q 17:88), not even a single surah is possible (Q 2:23; Q 10:38). It should be mentioned here that there is a surah in this Holy Qur'an which have only three verses (Q 108). All Muslims of the world believe these words, although they have theological differences. No significant mistake has been discovered in this scripture that has been scientifically proven. Therefore, grammatical or clerical errors are not taken into consideration in this study.

The Holy Qur'an has been duly and accurately sent down by Allah Almighty (Q 2:176; Q 3:3; Q 4:105; Q 5:48; Q 16:102; Q 17:105; Q 39:2; Q 39:41). At the same time, he has confirmed all the previous scriptures sent down through it (Q 3:3). It is also mentioned that every topic is analyzed with detailed explanation so that respective scholars can easily find answers to any question (Q 6:154; Q 10:37; Q 11:1; Q 17:41; Q 18:54; Q 30:58; 39:27; Q 75:19). Moreover, the author of the

Holy Qur'an himself is responsible for the edition and preservation (Q 15:9), so no person in the world can edit it in any way. However, people are not asked to blindly believe in this scripture, instead, the special urge has been given to the scholars to extract knowledge from it and do deep research (Q 12:111; Q 38:29; Q 40:54; Q 47:24). Therefore, inspired by this kind of motivation of the study of the Holy Qur'an, the author desires to find out what mystery is hidden in contrast of the spelling of the name of the same person.

2. Methodology

This article uses the method of content analysis to identify why two spelling rules are followed for the name of Ibrahim in the Holy Qur'an. Content analysis is a widely practiced research method that is a technique for the quantitative and qualitative study of communication messages in various formats, including text, audio, and visual. This type of approach allows researchers to determine the meaning, narrative, and themes of a data set, as well as the frequency with which words, concepts, and phrases are used (Hsieh and Shannon 2005). As this approach reflects the objective, methodological, and quantitative description of the overt content of communication (Berelson 1952; Flannelly et al 2004), it also serves as an integral part of the hypothesis-generating approach by specifically and systematically identifying specific features of messages (Barroga and Glafera 2022; Holsti 1969).

Since this study is not only interested in the frequency with which the words 'Ibrahim and Ibrahimi-m' are used in the Qur'an but to find out in-depth why they are used in such a way, a qualitative or interpretive approach is required. On the one hand, the application of content analysis as a qualitative and interpretive method allows the examination of narratives, descriptions of meaning, and contexts of communication, and enables researchers to code and analyze data, on the other hand, its focus on manifest content, which is literally or openly present, or latent content, which is not overtly apparent but implied or implicit in the text or message (Drisko and Maschi 2016; Elo et al 2014). We know that a surah of the Qur'an consists of several verses, so one verse is related to the verse before and after it, and even the content of that verse is related to different verses of different Surahs, which need to be studied to understand the matter deeply.

Recent studies show that a combination of methods has been used to study the Qur'an that includes content analysis, such as global development (Hanapi 2015; Salleh 2009), faith (Ali-Asghar and Otaghi. 2022; Ahmadzadeh 2019), environment (Sayem 2021; Helfaya et al. 2018), leadership, and management (Qasemi et al. 2018; Ozdasli and Aytar 2014), and masculinity (Mulligan 2022; Arat and Hasan 2018; Aslam 2014). There is a wide range of scholarly studies to analyze the content of the Holy Qur'an through the application of qualitative methods, such as the analysis of linguistic errors in Jihad (Bakircioglu 2010; Haleem 2010), the comparative review of the Holy Qur'an and the Holy Bible in the analysis of the magical events of Moses and Pharaoh (Witztum 2019; Smith 2018), and a groundbreaking analysis of the preaching of the Holy Qur'an in the Prophet Muhammad's community (Saleh 2018). All these studies demonstrate the value of content

analysis as a method of studying the Qur'an, that is, of expanding our knowledge of its surahs, verses, words, and letters.

3. Content Analysis of Ibrahim in the Holy Qur'an

The second surah (Al-Baqara) of the Holy Qur'an which is the largest of the 114 surahs contains a total of 286 verses. This surah is the main concept of all the contents of the Holy Qur'an. Verses 1-29 of the surah can be characterized as the introduction, verses 30-46 describe Adam and Iblis, and beginning with verse 47 addresses the Children of Israel, followed by verse 124 about Ibrahim. Only 15 different spellings of the name Ibrahim are mentioned in this Surah, so a deeper analysis of these verses is necessary. It is mentioned here consistently 11 times from verses 124 to 140 and 4 times towards the end of verses 258 and 260 which are identified as 12 contents and analyzed below.

Content: 1.1

And [mention, O Muhammad], when abraham was tried by his Lord with commands and he fulfilled them. [Allah] said, "Indeed, I will make you a leader for the people." [abraham] said, "And of my descendants?" [Allah] said, "My covenant does not include the wrongdoers." (Q 2:124)

The continuation of this verse begins originally from 122 where the children of Israel are said to be superior to everyone in the world. As mentioned in the verse above about Ibrahim, there are many facts behind him, that is, he was subjected to several tests and passed each one, as a result, he was promised by Allah Almighty to make him the leader of the entire human race. This promise is not only to him but also to his descendants. Therefore, from this verse, we can identify his tests and pedigree for further analysis.

Content: 1.2

And [mention] when We made the House a place of return for the people and [a place of] security. And take, [O believers], from the standing place of abraham a place of prayer. And We charged abraham and Ishmael, [saying], "Purify My House for those who perform Tawaf and those who are staying [there] for worship and those who bow and prostrate [in prayer]." (Q 2:125)

This verse is a continuation of the previous verse, but with a difference in content, that a house was assigned to mankind (not just Muslims) in place of Abraham's. Both are instructed to keep this house neat and clean and take a pledge that they will perform their duty properly. It may also be that this responsibility was also a test that revealed a connection with the previous verse. Since the same orthography is followed, therefore, no indication of name change is found.

Content: 1.3

And [mention] when Abraham said, "My Lord, make this a secure city and provide its people with fruits - whoever of them believes in Allah and the Last Day." [Allah] said. "And whoever disbelieves - I will grant him enjoyment for a little; then I will force him to the punishment of the Fire, and wretched is the destination." (Q 2:126)

Although the continuity of the verse is maintained, there is a revelation of new content here. Ibrahim prayed to God Almighty for the sustenance of the people of that city as well as for their safety. Allah accepts the condition in his prayer that those who do not come under the law of Allah, even if they get all the resources in this world, will be punished severely in the Hereafter. In this verse, none of the tests indicated for him are observed in the first content. This is a tough test for his city's population.

Content: 1.4

And [mention] when Abraham was raising the foundations of the House and [with him] Ishmael, [saying], "Our Lord, accept [this] from us. Indeed You are the Hearing, the Knowing. (Q 2:127)

However, the Holy Qur'an maintains continuity in this verse, the translator may have made some deviations from that continuity. Because the house was already there, it was written in the original language of the Qur'an, from which Abraham established the principles and prayed to Almighty Allah to accept it. Although this study is not a review of translation errors, rather than proceeding to a detailed explanation of the subject, let's find a connection with this study. Even based on traditional translations and Arabic texts, there is no such source could be found.

Content: 1.5

And who would be averse to the religion of abraham except one who makes a fool of himself. And We had chosen him in this world, and indeed he, in the Hereafter, will be among the righteous. (Q 2:130)

Although Ibrahim is described consistently in the above verse, the middle two verses do not directly mention him by name, therefore, it cannot be connected to this topic. The two verses mainly contain Ibrahim's prayer in which he pleads for the teaching of the rules of worship, for representatives among the descendants, for the creation of a strong group from the nation, and the sending of a Messenger. Almighty Allah accepted his request, which is revealed by mentioning his name in this verse. However, no indication of a spelling change of his name was found.

Content: 1.6

And abraham instructed his sons [to do the same] and [so did] Jacob, [saying], "O my sons, indeed Allah has chosen for you this religion, so do not die except while you are Muslims." (Q 2:132)

Again leaving out a verse where he was instructed to surrender to God Almighty and he surrendered accordingly. In this verse, adding the name of Jacob to the name of Ibrahim, both of them advise their children not to die without becoming Muslims. No information related to this study could be understood in this verse either.

Content: 1.7

Or were you witnesses when death approached Jacob, when he said to his sons, "What will you worship after me?" They said, "We will worship your God and the God of your fathers, abraham and Ishmael and Isaac - one God. And we are Muslims [in submission] to Him." (Q 2:133)

This verse is a continuation of the previous verse which mainly deals with the time of Jacob's death. In this verse, there is clear information about the genealogical relationship of Ibrahim, Ishmael, and Isaac with Jacob. This information may provide some clues to the analysis but is not directly relevant to this study.

Content: 1.8

They say, "Be Jews or Christians [so] you will be guided." Say, "Rather, [we follow] the religion of abraham, inclining toward truth, and he was not of the polytheists." (Q 2:135)

Again, it is seen that the name of Ibrahim comes directly except for one verse. These verses are a continuation of the narrative about Ibrahim that is witnessed in Ibrahim's monotheism. There is no connection between the earing of past and present nations. However, no significance information was available for analysis for this study.

Content: 1.9

Say, [O believers], "We have believed in Allah and what has been revealed to us and what has been revealed to abraham and Ishmael and Isaac and Jacob and the Descendants and what was given to Moses and Jesus and what was given to the prophets from their Lord. We make no distinction between any of them, and we are Muslims [in submission] to Him." (Q 2:136)

This verse is very important because the basic formula of becoming a Muslim is written down by Allah Almighty, although no Muslim sect recites this verse as an oath. They have their oath according to their respective sects. As this type of analysis is not relevant to this study, thus, a detailed discussion is omitted. Not only Ibrahim but also Ishmael, Isaac, Moses, Jesus, Jacob, and their children are mentioned as believing and approving of all the scriptures. Nothing that descends to them can be distinguished. For this study, even if something is not directly observed in this verse, it can be helped to get the expected outcome.

Content: 1.10

Or do you say that abraham and Ishmael and Isaac and Jacob and the Descendants were Jews or Christians? Say, "Are you more knowing or is Allah?" And who is more unjust than one who conceals a testimony he has from Allah? And Allah is not unaware of what you do. (Q 2:140)

This verse comes in the continuation of the narrative about Ibrahim. The preceding three verses only give an idea of the consequences of belief and disbelief in monotheism. The gist of this verse is that apart from Ibrahim, Ishmael, Isaac, Jacob and their children were all believers in one God and were devoted to its affirmation. It is to be noted here that from verse 47 there is a break in Ibrahim's relationship between the various narratives of the Bani Isra'il. However, no direct significant information was found in this series of discussions to make the purpose of this study successful.

Content: 1.11

Have you not considered the one who argued with abraham about his Lord [merely] because Allah had given him kingship? When abraham said, "My Lord is the one who gives life and causes death," he said, "I give life and cause death." abraham said, "Indeed, Allah brings up the sun from the east, so bring it up from the west." So the disbeliever was overwhelmed [by astonishment], and Allah does not guide the wrongdoing people. (Q 2:258)

In this verse, Ibrahim had a reasoned argument with the ruler. It should be noted here that the order in which this verse appears shows the description of the special qualities that one Prophet gave to another. Perhaps to preserve that continuity, some of Ibrahim's particular highlights are resumed from this verse. Two important points are highlighted in this verse, the first is the irrefutable argument about the Creator, and the second, Allah has given him sovereignty. However, nothing directly related to the name was found in this verse either.

Content: 1.12

And [mention] when abraham said, "My Lord, show me how You give life to the dead." [Allah] said, "Have you not believed?" He said, "Yes, but [I ask] only that my heart may be satisfied." [Allah] said, "Take four birds and commit them to yourself. Then [after slaughtering them] put on each hill a portion of them; then call them - they will come [flying] to you in haste. And know that Allah is Exalted in Might and Wise." (Q 2:260)

This verse is a continuation of the previous verse, but verse 259 describes an event that is probably closely related to this verse. Basically, through the bird, Ibrahim is shown how Almighty Allah resurrects the dead. This verse is the last in the first spelling. Unfortunately, there is also no direct or indirect information found to this study in this verse either.

Now the second orthography is mentioned 54 times in 25 Surah's and is included in the 25 contents analyzed below.

Content: 2.1

Indeed, Allah chose Adam and Noah and the family of abraham and the family of 'Imran over the worlds. (Q 3:2)

It is from this verse that the second spell begins. Here not only Ibrahim but Adam, Noah, and Imran have chosen the family of four over creation. In the next verse, it is mentioned that they are descendants of each other. Since similar comments were made about these four individuals, thus, logically, there is no association was found in this study.

Content: 2.2

O People of the Scripture, why do you argue about abraham while the Torah and the Gospel were not revealed until after him? Then will you not reason? (Q 3:65) abraham was neither a Jew nor a Christian, but he was one inclining toward truth, a Muslim [submitting to Allah]. And he was not of the polytheists. (Q 3:67) Indeed, the most worthy of abraham among the people are those who followed him [in submission to Allah] and this prophet, and those who believe [in his message]. And Allah is the ally of the believers. (Q 3:68)

Verses 65-68 are analyzed together here because we have analyzed almost similar sentences earlier in the first spelling. Although the words of the verses seem to be the same, there is a special difference, those words were addressed to the Children of Israel and here it is said to the people of the scriptures.

Content: 2.3

Say, "We have believed in Allah and in what was revealed to us and what was revealed to abraham, Ishmael, Isaac, Jacob, and the Descendants, and in what was given to Moses and Jesus and to the prophets from their Lord. We make no distinction between any of them, and we are Muslims [submitting] to Him." (Q 3:84)

This verse is exactly in (Q 2:136), so it is analyzed there. The only difference between the two verses is that in the former verse, it is spoken in the plural (Your) and here in the singular (You).

Content: 2.4

Say, "Allah has told the truth. So follow the religion of abraham, inclining toward truth; and he was not of the polytheists." (Q 3:95) In it are clear signs [such as] the standing place of abraham. And whoever enters it shall be safe. And [due] to Allah from the people is a pilgrimage to the House - for whoever is able to find thereto a way. But whoever disbelieves - then indeed, Allah is free from need of the worlds. (Q 3:97)

Here the two verses are analyzed together. From verses 95 to 97, the words that have been said consecutively, have been said before in the instructions of the children of Israel, and here referring to the people of the scriptures, it is called the first house by Allah (Q 3:96). Since it is not related to this study, it is not analyzed in detail.

Content: 2.5

Or do they envy people for what Allah has given them of His bounty? But we had already given the family of abraham the Scripture and wisdom and conferred upon them a great kingdom. (Q 4:45) And who is better in religion than one who submits himself to Allah while being a doer of good and follows the religion of abraham, inclining toward truth? And Allah took abraham as an intimate friend. (Q 4: 125) Indeed, We have revealed to you, [O Muhammad], as We revealed to Noah and the prophets after him. And we revealed to abraham, Ishmael, Isaac, Jacob, the Descendants, Jesus, Job, Jonah, Aaron, and Solomon, and to David We gave the book [of Psalms]. (Q 4:163)

In this context, three isolated verses of the same Surah are analyzed together. These verses are presented to describe different events, which are somewhat similar to the previously analyzed verses. The last verse contains very important information which is a chrome list of prophets who received the revelation that may have helped the discussion later in this study.

Content: 2.5

And [mention, O Muhammad], when abraham said to his father Azar, "Do you take idols as deities? Indeed, I see you and your people to be in manifest error." (Q 6:74) And thus did We show abraham the realm of the heavens and the earth that he would be among the certain [in faith] (Q 6:75) And that was Our [conclusive] argument which We gave abraham against his people. We raise by degrees whom We will. Indeed, your Lord is Wise and Knowing. (Q 6:83) And We gave to abraham, Isaac and Jacob - all [of them] We guided. And Noah, We guided before; and among his descendants, David and Solomon and Job and Joseph and Moses and Aaron. Thus do We reward the doers of good. (Q 6:161)

The descriptions of Ibrahim are analyzed together in this surah from 74 to 87 consecutively and in verse 161 alone. Most of the first sequence repeats the same that is the words conveyed to the people of the scriptures and elaborates on the debate that was conceived in the verse mentioned earlier (2:258). Finally, in verse 161, Ibrahim's devotion is mentioned. However, no special information related to this study was found in these verses.

Content: 2.6

Has there not reached them the news of those before them - the people of Noah and [the tribes of] 'Aad and Thamud and the people of abraham and the companions of Madyan and the towns overturned? Their messengers came to them with clear proofs. And Allah would never have wronged them, but they were wronging themselves. (Q 9:70) And the

request of forgiveness of abraham for his father was only because of a promise he had made to him. But when it became apparent to abraham that his father was an enemy to Allah, he disassociated himself from him. Indeed was abraham compassionate and patient. (Q 9:114)

The name of Ibrahim occurs in two different contexts in the narration of various subjects in the ninth surah, which are analyzed together here. First of all, the story of Ibrahim's nation came while describing various events of the previous nations. The second point is that if someone in the family is even their father, they are unforgivable to Allah Almighty, so no supplication should be made for them. In these verses, no significant source related to this study was found.

Content: 2.7

And certainly did Our messengers come to abraham with good tidings; they said, "Peace." He said, "Peace," and did not delay in bringing [them] a roasted calf. (Q 11:69) And when the fright had left abraham and the good tidings had reached him, he began to argue with Us concerning the people of Lot. (Q 11:74) Indeed, abraham was forbearing, grieving and [frequently] returning [to Allah]. (Q 11:75) [The angels said], "O abraham, give up this [plea]. Indeed, the command of your Lord has come, and indeed, there will reach them a punishment that cannot be repelled." (Q 11:76)

These four verses come separately to describe the various historical events of the nations of Ad and Thamud, so they are analyzed together. Although no significant information is found in the verses mentioning Ibrahim here, the narrative reveals that he received the good news of children in his old age, especially Isaac and Ya'qub after Isaac (11:71), which may provide some link to this study.

Content: 2.8

And thus will your Lord choose you and teach you the interpretation of narratives and complete His favor upon you and upon the family of Jacob, as He completed it upon your fathers before, abraham and Isaac. Indeed, your Lord is Knowing and Wise." (Q 12:6) And I have followed the religion of my fathers, abraham, Isaac and Jacob. And it was not for us to associate anything with Allah. That is from the favor of Allah upon us and upon the people, but most of the people are not grateful. (Q 12:38)

In this surah, Ibrahim's name is directly mentioned in two verses while describing the events of the descendants of Ibrahim from Jacob to Yusuf, especially the Prophet Yusuf. There is no significant information directly or indirectly related to this study other than the confirmation of the Prophets who came from the line of Ibrahim.

Content: 2.9

And [mention, O Muhammad], when abraham said, "My Lord, make this city [Makkah] secure and keep me and my sons away from worshipping idols. (Q 14:35)

This surah is named after Ibrahim himself, but his name appears directly once as a noun in this verse, and all other places pronouns are used. There are two important facts here firstly a city and secondly sons (the plural). These two facts have been analyzed in different ways in the history of Islam, and since they do not appear to be directly relevant to this study, they are not analyzed here. Moreover, all the descriptions using pronouns are prayers about these two issues.

Content: 2.9

And inform them about the guests of abraham, (Q 15:51)

In this verse, the name of Ibrahim comes from the angel's quotation with Ibrahim to describe the destruction of the people of Lot. However, no significant variable related to this study was found.

Content: 2.10

Indeed, abraham was a [comprehensive] leader, devoutly obedient to Allah, inclining toward truth, and he was not of those who associate others with Allah. (Q 16:120) Then We revealed to you, [O Muhammad], to follow the religion of abraham, inclining toward truth; and he was not of those who associate with Allah. (Q 16:123)

Although the name of Ibrahim is mentioned here in two isolated verses, the Holy Qur'an informs the revealed Prophet about him continuously from verses 120 to 124. The reference to the exalted status of Ibrahim and to following his religion, although this verse has caused considerable confusion in mainstream Islam. As those issues are not covered in this study, a detailed analysis is not done. However, no significant information was found for this study.

Content: 2.11

And mention in the Book [the story of] abraham. Indeed, he was a man of truth and a prophet. (Q 19:41) [His father] said, "Have you no desire for my gods, O abraham? If you do not desist, I will surely stone you, so avoid me a prolonged time." (Q 19:46) Those were the ones upon whom Allah bestowed favor from among the prophets of the descendants of Adam and of those We carried [in the ship] with Noah, and of the descendants of abraham and Israel, and of those whom We guided and chose. When the verses of the Most Merciful were recited to them, they fell in prostration and weeping. (Q 19:58)

From 141 to 160 of this surah successive arguments with Ibrahim's father are discussed in detail, and the three verses that mention his name separately are analyzed together. Consistent with this study, no significant variables were found by reviewing this series of verses.

Content: 2.12

And We had certainly given abraham his sound judgement before, and We were of him well-Knowing (Q 21:51) They said, "We heard a young man mention them who is called abraham." (Q 21:60) They said, "Have you done this to our gods, O abraham? (Q 21:62) Allah said, "O fire, be coolness and safety upon abraham." (Q 21:69)

From 151 to 170 of this surah continuously several historical events of Ibrahim are described in detail, and the four verses that mention his name separately are analyzed together. As these events did not appear to be related to the study, they were not analyzed in detail. That is, by reviewing this series of verses, no information was found that was consistent with this study.

Content: 2.13

And [mention, O Muhammad], when We designated for abraham the site of the House, [saying], "Do not associate anything with Me and purify My House for those who perform Tawaf and those who stand [in prayer] and those who bow and prostrate. (Q 22:26) And the people of abraham and the people of Lot (Q 22:43) And strive for Allah with the striving due to Him. He has chosen you and has not placed upon you in the religion any difficulty. [It is] the religion of your father, abraham. Allah named you "Muslims" before [in former scriptures] and in this [revelation] that the Messenger may be a witness over you and you may be witnesses over the people. So establish prayer and give zakah and hold fast to Allah. He is your protector; and excellent is the protector, and excellent is the helper. (Q 22:78)

From verse 26 of this surah, the rules of Hajj of Ibrahim are described in detail to the Prophet to whom the Qur'an was revealed, which continues up to verse 37. Starting from verse 38 describing the rules of war, from verse 42 onwards various historical events of Nuh, 'Ad, the people of Thamud and later the people of Ibrahim are described. Finally, the surah ends by introducing Ibrahim as the father of all. Since he is identified as the father, there may be some connection with this study.

Content: 2.14

And recite to them the news of abraham, (Q 26:69)

Starting from verse 69 of this Surah, the description of various events of Ibrahim continues up to verse 104. The reader of these verses did not find any important information that could apply to this study.

Content: 2.15

And [We sent] abraham, when he said to his people, "Worship Allah and fear Him. That is best for you, if you should know. (Q 29:16) And when Our messengers came to abraham with the good tidings, they said, "Indeed, we will destroy the people of that Lot's city. Indeed, its people have been wrongdoers." (Q 29:31)

Verses 16 to 35 of this surah outline the various histories of the destruction of the nations of Ibrahim and Lot. In two places Ibrahim's name is mentioned directly, and in most places', the pronouns are used. A careful review of these verses did not reveal any content that could be relevant to this study.

Content: 2.16

And [mention, O Muhammad], when We took from the prophets their covenant and from you and from Noah and abraham and Moses and Jesus, the son of Mary; and We took from them a solemn covenant. (Q 37:7)

This verse discusses taking covenant from all the prophets and mentions the name of Ibrahim along with some of the prophets. Since there is no single characteristic of Ibrahim, thus, there is no significant aspect to this study.

Content: 2.17

And indeed, among his kind was abraham, (Q 37:83) We called to him, "O abraham, (Q 37:104) "Peace upon abraham." (Q 37:109)

Verses 83 to 113 of this surah describe various historical events of Ibrahim in detail, some of which are repeated. However, verse 108 says " And We left for him [favorable mention] among later generations: ", which probably needs to be closely observed to see if it implies any kind of association with this study.

Content: 2.18

And remember Our servants, abraham, Isaac and Jacob - those of strength and [religious] vision. (Q 38:45)

In this verse, Ibrahim's name is mentioned to describe the status of various prophets, that is, no special characteristic of him is referred separately. It is noted that although many attributes are prescribed in successive verses, they are also applied to other Prophets, so no important information related to this study was found.

Content: 2.19

He has ordained for you of religion what He enjoined upon Noah and that which We have revealed to you, [O Muhammad], and what We enjoined upon abraham and Moses and Jesus - to establish the religion and not be divided therein. Difficult for those who associate others with Allah is that to which you invite them. Allah chooses for Himself whom He wills and guides to Himself whoever turns back [to Him]. (Q 42:13)

In this verse, even though no important variable seems to be related to this study, however, one significant issue can be found, such as Allah Almighty has ordained the religion of the Prophet Noah and later sent revelation to the prophets continually. Basic statutory provisions have changed over the ages as people have distorted them to their convenience. Almighty Allah ordered all human groups to belong to one group.

Content: 2.20

And [mention, O Muhammad], when abraham said to his father and his people, "Indeed, I am disassociated from that which you worship (Q 43:26)

Although there is a description of Ibrahim from verses 26 to 30, unfortunately, there is no significant information related to this article was found.

Content: 2.21

Has there reached you the story of the honored guests of abraham? (Q 51:24)

In this surah verses 24 to 37 describe in detail the good news of Ibrahim's children and the punishment of a community during that period. However, after a review of all the verses, no important information related to this study was found

Content: 2.22

And [of] abraham, who fulfilled [his obligations] (Q 53:37)

To describe the various scriptures, different discussions continue by referring to the scripture of Ibrahim in this verse only. No significant information related to this study was found for detailed analysis.

Content: 2.23

And We have already sent Noah and abraham and placed in their descendants prophethood and scripture; and among them is he who is guided, but many of them are defiantly disobedient. (Q 57:26)

In this verse, Noah and Ibrahim are discussed together as most of their progeny were unbelievers. Although there is much significant information available for genealogy research, however, there is not much fruitful information for this study.

Content: 2.24

There has already been for you an excellent pattern in abraham and those with him, when they said to their people, "Indeed, we are disassociated from you and from whatever you worship other than Allah. We have denied you, and there has appeared between us and you animosity and hatred forever until you believe in Allah alone" except for the saying of abraham to his father, "I will surely ask forgiveness for you, but I have not [power to do] for you anything against Allah. Our Lord, upon You we have relied, and to You we have returned, and to You is the destination. (Q 60:4)

The verses that follow this verse describe Ibrahim's prayers, especially his harshness towards the disbelievers of his time and show of leniency towards his father. Although these verses are of great importance in theology, the verses are in no way relevant to this study.

Content: 2.25

The scriptures of abraham and Moses. (Q 87:19)

In the Holy Qur'an, Ibrahim's name is consistently ended with this verse of this Surah. Since Ibrahim and Moses are mentioned here together, there is no special discussion separately, it could not be selected for further analysis or discussion in this study.

4. Discussion

In the above analysis, 12 in the first spelling and 25 in the second spelling, a total of 37 contents along with almost all the related verses in the Holy Qur'an were reviewed. Unfortunately, no direct source of this spelling discrepancy has been found anywhere. We have therefore identified a few points that may be indirectly involved, which we will discuss in detail below.

In the light of content 1.1, all the tests and genealogy of Ibrahim as described in the Holy Qur'an could not find any source, which could have any influence on the results of this study. Content: In 2.5 we hoped that some significant information might be found in the description of Ibrahim's descendants before and after nothing was found there either. Similarly, content: 2.7 contains various events related to Isaac, Isaac, and Jacob after the gospel we fail to uncover the main mystery of this study.

Even in the light of the minimum probability of all the verses, the explanation of this spelling discrimination was found somewhere in the Holy Qur'an, so one of the most important points comes to our attention, that is Content: 1.9 and Content: 2.3, where there is no difference between all the words and their meaning, except, only in the beginning say it (قُولُوا) (Q 2:136) and say (قُلْ) (Q 3:84) whereas two types spelling for Ibrahim. There cannot be a grammatical explanation in this case, because there are two sentences of the same words, and only the person's spelling is different. So we have abandoned grammatical analysis altogether. This study has highlighted the aim and intention of these two verses, that is, to be a Muslim, one must come under this belief, which is called the universal oath of Islam.

The same universal speech of the Holy Qur'an authorizes us to believe in the scriptures of Abraham, Ishmael, Isaac, Jacob, Moses, and Jesus, so our search for those scriptures becomes very important for this study. Although there are sectarian differences, all Muslims believe in the Torah and Injil, the scriptures of Moses and Jesus, which are now the Old and New Testament of the Holy Bible, although Muslims believe that these two scriptures are not completely incorrupt but not completely corrupted (Saleh 2008). Since this study will not influence any of the three religions with any kind of religious practice, therefore, the biblical information in this study cannot cause any kind of conflict. To find answers to these research questions we therefore delve into two testaments of the Holy Bible. Surprisingly, we find all our solutions very easily, that is Ibrahim's name is spelled in two different ways in the Holy Bible (Abram and Abraham).

When Abram was ninety-nine years old, the Lord appeared to him and said, "I am God Almighty; walk before me faithfully and be blameless. Then I will make my covenant between me and you and will greatly increase your numbers." Abram fell facedown, and God said to him, "As for me, this is my covenant with you: You will be the father of many nations. No longer will you be called Abram; your name will be Abraham, for I have made you a father of many nations. I will make you very fruitful; I will make nations of you, and kings will come from you. I will establish my covenant as an everlasting covenant between me and you and your descendants after you for the generations to come, to be your God and the God of your descendants after you. The whole land of Canaan, where you now reside as a foreigner, I will give as an everlasting possession to you and your descendants after you; and I will be their God." (OLD TESTAMENT: Genesis: Chapter 17: 1-8)

According to Genesis: Chapter 17: 1-8, we see that Abram carried the name given to his family for 99 years and the Lord changed his name to Abraham. Therefore, in the light of the Holy Bible, Abram means the father of a nation, and the grammar that the Lord has made plural is Abraham, that is, the father of many nations. The evidence in support of this statement is found in the first content (Q 2:124) where Allah promised Abraham that he would be made the leader of the human race. The entire human was initially one race that later divided into different nations, thus, sufficient consistency with this promise is found in the Holy Qur'an.

We can also explain that since the second surah of the Holy Qur'an is marked as the introductory chapter to the entire Qur'an, perhaps Almighty Allah has retained the first name of Ibrahim in every place of this surah. In many verses in the Holy Qur'an, the scholars are given a special status and instructed to do in-depth thinking and research (Q 3:19; Q 3:191; Q 4: 82; Q 7:176; Q 13:4; Q 16:44; Q 23:68; Q 39:42; Q 88:17), so without based on these two verses (Q 2:136) and (Q 3:84), it will never be possible to understand the spelling of Ibrahim (Q 7:157). The Holy Qur'an clearly describes this mystery with the name of Ibrahim, but we have not found the correct answer even after analyzing all the verses about him.

Now the question may arise whether the Ibrahim mentioned in the Holy Qur'an and Abraham of the Bible are the same person or not, but there are many studies about this. Since this study does not aim to resolve such controversies, a detailed discussion is not done here. The Muslim world irrefutably believes that there is no difference between Ibrahim and Isa (Abraham and Jesus) of the Muslims as mentioned in the Holy Bible (Morteza 2023; Bashir et al 2022; Rumaisah 2022; Mirza 2011; Ben-Ari 2007; Goshen-Gottstein 2002). They only differ in the content of worship in the Torah, Injil, and Qur'an. The basic objective of this study was to find out the explanation for the discrepancy in the spelling of Ibrahim. It was found with the help of the Holy Bible detailed information about the accuracy of the Holy Qur'an.

It should be noted here that the OLD TESTAMENT: Genesis: Chapter 17: 1-8 describes him and his descendants, all the facts consistent with what we see from the content of 2.1 above to the last verse through different densities. In the beginning, the continuity of Abraham's family and their

names are clearly stated, keeping this line intact, the descendants of Abraham are mentioned up to Jesus and he is called the father of the nations (22:78). Even today, despite the differences in their perceptions, Abraham is the same person to the people of all three major religions.

5. Conclusions

This study was started with a question that should be easily answered by all of us as the Holy Qur'an has existed historically for more than 1400 years among all people including the Muslim world. Unfortunately, it is a fact that there is no scientific explanation that can enrich our knowledge about this issue. Two spellings of the same person in one scripture is naturally marked as a clerical error, but the Holy Qur'an continues with the spelling without any explanation, which is surprising to think. Since there is no significant grammar in spelling a person's name, and what there is, it is not possible to solve this type of problem, so this study is done through content analysis.

The name of Ibrahim is mentioned 69 times in 63 verses of different surahs of the Holy Qur'an divided into 12 contents (15 times) for the first spelling and 25 contents (54 times) for the second spelling and all related verses were analyzed. There is no direct evidence of this spelling discrimination anywhere in the Holy Qur'an. Therefore, by analyzing the OLD TESTAMENT: Genesis: Chapter 17:1-8 of the Holy Qur'an approved by the Holy Bible, it was found that Abraham had two names there too. Abram is the name given to his family, meaning leader of a nation, and Abraham is the name given by the Lord, meaning leader of many nations. Therefore, it was concluded in the study that there is no clerical or grammatical error in these two types of spelling in the Holy Qur'an and there is no different interpretation.

This study is a breakthrough result in theology, firstly in the systematic aspect as all the content is taken from two holy scriptures of two religions, however, both religions have different doctrines, and there is no controversy between these scriptures, therefore, this study is a methodological bridge. Second, the results also confirm that, although there are many branches of Abrahamic religion, however, there is no difference between individual Ibrahim. The main limitation of this study, despite being careful, is that it is unable to answer any questions based on Islamic School in orthography because no such texts were included in this analysis.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: This study did not require ethical approval.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declares no conflict of interest.

Note:

1. All the English translations of the Holy Qur'an are taken from 2004. THE QUR'AN, English Meanings English Revised and Edited by Saheeh International, Jeddah, KSA, ISBN: 9960-792-63-3.
2. Part of the Holy Bible has been taken from THE OLD TESTAMENT Published by The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints, Salt Lake City, Utah, USA, Printed in the United States of America 4/2014.
3. Since this article is meant to explain spelling differences, therefore, a few of the spellings used in English Ibrahim, Ibrahi-i-m, Abrahm, and Abraham are used.

References

- Ahmadzadeh, Sayyed Mostafa. 2019. The Meaning of Faith in the Holy Qur'an by Qualitative Content Analysis Method. *Qur'an and Hadith Studies* 12: 135–64.
- Ali-Asghar, Sharifi-Rad, and Masoumeh, Otaghi. 2022. The relevance between faith to God and health dimensions in the Holy Qur'an: A content analysis. *International Journal of Health Sciences* 6:5342–5351.
- Arat, Zehra F. Kabasakal, and Abdullah Hasan. 2018. Muslim masculinities: What is the prescription of the Qur'an? *Journal of Gender Studies* 27: 788–801.
- Aslam, Maleeha. 2014. Islamism and Masculinity: Case Study Pakistan. *Historical Social Research*, Special Issue: Terrorism, Gender, and History. State of Research, Concepts, Case Studies 39:135-149.
- Barroga, Edward, and Glafera, Janet Matanguihan. 2022. A Practical Guide to Writing Quantitative and Qualitative Research Questions and Hypotheses in Scholarly Articles. *Journal of Korean Medical Science* 37: e121.
- Bakircioglu, Onder. 2010. *A Socio-Legal Analysis of the Concept of Jihad*. Cambridge University Press.
- Bashir, Ishfaq, Raveendran, K, and Thangaivelan, S. 2022. Religions Quest for Peace: A Comparative Study of Abrahamic Religions (Christianity, Islam, and Judaism). *Neuro Quantology* 20: 820-835.
- Ben-Ari, Shosh. 2007. The Stories about Abraham in Islam. A Geographical Approach. *Arabica* 54:526-553.
- Berelson, Bernard. 1952. *Content Analysis in Communication Research*. New York: Free Press.
- Cooper, Adam G. 2000. 'In the Bosom of Abraham': Identity and formation of Christians as 'Sons of Abraham' in the early church. *Lutheran Theological Journal; Adelaide* 34: 116.

- Drisko, James, and Tina Maschi. 2016. *Content Analysis. Pocket Guide to Social Work Research Methods*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Elo, Satu, Kääriäinen, Maria, Kanste, Outi, Pölkki, Tarja, Utriainen, Kati and Kyngäs, Helvi. 2014. Qualitative Content Analysis: A Focus on Trustworthiness. *SAGE Open* January-March: 1–10
- Feldman, Jackie. 2011. Abraham the Settler, Jesus the Refugee: Contemporary Conflict and Christianity on the Road to Bethlehem. *History and Memory* 23: 62-95.
- Flannelly, Kevin J, Weaver, Andrew J, and Costa, Karen G. 2004. A systematic review of religion and spirituality in three palliative care journals, 1990-1999. *Journal of Palliative Care* 20:50-56.
- Goshen-Gottstein, Alon. 2002. Abraham and ‘Abrahamic Religions’ in Contemporary Interreligious Discourse. *Studies in Interreligious Dialogue* 12:165-183.
- Gregory, Bradley C. 2008. Abraham as the Jewish Ideal: Exegetical Traditions in Sirach. *The Catholic Biblical Quarterly* 44:19-21.
- Hall, Robert G. 1988. The "Christian Interpolation" in the Apocalypse of Abraham. *Journal of Biblical Literature* 107: 107-110.
- Haleem, MAS Abdel. 2010. Qur'anic ‘jih^{ad}’: A Linguistic and Contextual Analysis. *Journal of Qur'anic Studies* 12: 147–66.
- Hanapi, Mohd Shukri. 2015. A Content Analysis on Verses Related with Development Worldview in the Qur'an. *Sains Humanika* 5: 87–98.
- Helfaya, Akrum, Amr Kotb, and Rasha Hanafi. 2018. Qur'anic ethics for environmental responsibility: Implications for business practice. *Journal of Business Ethics* 150: 1105–28.
- Hsieh, Hsiu-Fang, and Shannon, Sarah E. 2005. Three Approaches to Qualitative Content Analysis. *Qualitative Health Research* 15:1277-1288.
- Holsti, Ole R. 1969. *Content Analysis for the Social Sciences and Humanities*. Reading: Addison-Wesley.
- Mirza, Younus. 2011. Abraham as an iconoclast: Understanding the destruction of ‘images’ through Qur'anic exegesis. *Islam and Christian–Muslim Relations* 16: 413-428.
- Mojzes, Paul. 2022. Review of Our Father Abraham: Jewish Roots of the Christian Faith, by Marvin R. Wilson. *Journal of Ecumenical Studies* 57: 164-166.
- Morteza, Agha Mohammadi. 2023. A Comparative Study of “the Words” the Prophet Ibrahim Was Tested with. *Journal of Ahl al-Bayt (as) Teachings* 1:47-62.

- Mulligan, Kieran. 2022. Muslim Masculinity, the Media, and the Medieval Period. *Spectrum* 11:1-13.
- Ozdasli, Kursat, and Oguzhan Aytar. 2014. A Content Analysis on Management and Terms related with Management in the Qur'an. *Eurasian Journal of Business and Economics* 7: 157–72.
- Qasemi, Hamid Reza, Farahani, Fatemeh Akbari, and Roodsari, Mahboubeh Ranjkesh. 2018. Talent Management Components from the Perspective of the Qur'an. *Human Resource Management Research* 8: 49-62.
- Rumaisah, Murobbiyah Auliya. 2022. Israeliyyatin The Story of the Son of the Prophet Ibrahim.: Comparative Study of the Interpretation of Surah As-Saffat 99-113 By Mufassir from Classical to Contemporary Eras. *ULIL ALBAB: Jurnal Ilmiah Multidisiplin* 1:3727–3735.
- Saleh, Walid A. 2008. A Fifteenth-Century Muslim Hebraist: Al-Biqā'ī and His Defense of Using the Bible to Interpret the Qur'ān. *Speculum* 83:629.
- Saleh, Walid A. 2018. The Preacher of the Meccan Qur'an: Deuteronomistic History and Confessionalism in Muhammad's Early Preaching. *Journal of Qur'anic Studies* 20: 74–111.
- Salleh, Muhammad Syukri. 2009. The Philosophical Foundations of Islamic Development: Khurshid Ahmad's Conception Revisited. In *Proceedings Langkawi Islamic Finance and Economics International Conference (LIFE2009)*: 119–133. Kedah: Kolej Universiti INSANIAH (KUIN).
- Sayem, Md Abu. 2021. Islam and Environmental Ethics. *Islamic Studies* 60:157-172.
- Siker, Jeffrey S. 2009. Abraham, Paul, and the Politics of Christian Identity. *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 16: 56-70.
- Smith, Andrew. 2018. Moses and Pharaoh's Magicians: A Discursive Analysis of the Qur'anic Narratives in the Light of Late Antique Texts and Traditions. *Journal of Qur'anic Studies* 20: 67–104.
- Witztum, Joseph. 2019. Pharaoh and His Council: Great Minds Think Alike. *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 139:945-952.

Annexure: I

The name Ibrahim is mentioned in all the verses of the Holy Qur'an

1st form (إبرهـم)			2nd form (إبرهـيم)			
SL	Verse	Verse	Verse	Verse	Verse	Verse
1.	2:124	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	3:33	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	16:123	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
2.	2:125	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	3:65	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	19:41	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
3.	2:125	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	3:67	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	19:46	يَا إِبْرَاهِيمَ
4.	2:126	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	3:68	يَا إِبْرَاهِيمَ	19:58	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
5.	2:127	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	3:84	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	21:51	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
6.	2:130	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	3:95	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	21:60	يَا إِبْرَاهِيمَ
7.	2:132	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	3:97	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	21:62	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
8.	2:133	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	4:54	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	21:69	لِإِبْرَاهِيمَ
9.	2:135	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	4:125	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	22:26	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
10.	2:136	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	4:125	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	22:43	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
11.	2:140	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	4:163	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	22:78	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
12.	2:258	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	6:74	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	26:69	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
13.	2:258	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	6:75	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	29:16	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
14.	2:258	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	6:83	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	29:31	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
15.	2:260	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	6:161	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	33:7	لِإِبْرَاهِيمَ
16.			9:70	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	37:83	يَا إِبْرَاهِيمَ
17.			9:114	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	37:104	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
18.			9:114	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	37:109	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
19.			11:69	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	38:45	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
20.			11:74	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	42:138	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
21.			11:75	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	43:26	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
22.			11:76	يَا إِبْرَاهِيمَ	51:24	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
23.			12:6	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	53:37	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
24.			12:38	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	57:26	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
25.			14:35	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	60:4	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
26.			15:51	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	60:4	إِبْرَاهِيمَ
27.			16:120	إِبْرَاهِيمَ	87:19	إِبْرَاهِيمَ